

SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS ARE THE FOUNDATION OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN

Rahmonova Sanoat Shuhrat qizi

Teacher of History and philology department, Asia International University

rahmonovasanoatshuhratqizi@oxu.uz

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Abstract. *This article examines the importance of the poet Maksud Sheikhzoda's work in forming a sense of patriotism in today's youth and the problems of educating young people in the spirit of love for the Motherland. In the author's opinion, the main goal of educating young people in the spirit of love for the Motherland in higher educational institutions is to educate them through the educational process and prepare them as spiritually mature specialists.*

Keywords: *traditions, youth, spirit, spiritual person, patriotism, education, patriotic education, modern education, Homeland, poetry, goals, traditions, youth, spiritual person.*

ДУХОВНО-ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ РЕФОРМЫ — ОСНОВА НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается значение творчества поэта Максуда Шейхзода в формировании чувства патриотизма у современной молодежи и проблемы воспитания молодежи в духе любви к Родине. По мнению автора, главная цель воспитания молодежи в духе любви к Родине в высших учебных заведениях — это воспитание ее через образовательный процесс и подготовка ее как духовно зрелых специалистов.*

Ключевые слова: *традиции, молодежь, дух, духовная личность, патриотизм, образование, патриотическое воспитание, современное образование, Родина, поэзия, цели, традиции, молодежь, духовная личность.*

The rise of worldview, thinking and social consciousness in man was formed as a result of the need to live in society, and he began to feel the need for the environment around him, for people and human relationships. As a result, a spiritual and enlightened worldview was formed in man. Spirituality is not only a set of historical and traditional values It is not a separate reality, but a reality that complements and harmonizes with the way a person lives. There have been different ideas about the formation of spirituality in different periods, and most of them were formed in proportion to the realities of the past. Most scholars limit their research on spirituality to the past, not connecting it with the current goals and objectives of the present. In modern developed countries, the values of civil society are:

- popular power, the functioning of government based on the interests of citizens,
- political decision-making by majority vote, respect for minority rights,

- guarantees for the implementation of fundamental human rights,
- the establishment of a free and fair electoral system, equality before the law for all,
- the establishment of a fair judiciary, pluralism of worldviews, Values such as

tolerance of different views and opinions have become an integral and inseparable part of the spirituality and culture of every member of society. Today, our country has set itself the goal of achieving the level of socio-economic development of developed countries and is moving towards the noble goal of building a new Uzbek society. In the history of every nation and people, there are periods of renewal, when the nation's striving for goodness, inventions and discoveries are evaluated by their high heights. Spiritual and educational work has played a leading role in the commonality of such noble goals, not only in the present era, but in every era. In such processes, there is a need to preserve peace and tranquility, as a state with its own unique and worthy place in the world community, to deeply study the heritage of our ancestors, and to elevate these traditions to a higher level. One of the main goals of developing spirituality is to ensure that the large-scale reforms being implemented in our country reach the minds and hearts of all members of all strata of our society, to form a high civic position in them, and to educate young people who are not indifferent to the fate of their homeland. In order to build and develop a new society in the country, first of all, paying significant attention to the human factor and forming spiritually high people is one of the important directions of state policy. Therefore, the unification and cohesion of all citizens living in society around such basic goals as national and spiritual values will further improve their activities. From the earliest times of the creation of humanity to the present day, efforts to build a just society with vital and human amenities have continued. From the earliest times of history, attention has been paid to the development of moral and spiritual values as an invaluable factor in maintaining the stability of society in building a just society. It is precisely on this basis that scientific, socio-philosophical and religious views on the ideal vision of an ideal society were formed. Special importance is attached to widely acquainting not only our people, but also the world community with the services to the Motherland and the people, the invaluable scientific and creative heritage of our great scholars and thinkers who have left an indelible mark on the history of our national spirituality. As is known, the land of Central Asia is one of the ancient cradles of Islamic science and culture. Comprehensive study of the rich historical, scientific, and spiritual heritage of our people, in-depth disclosure of the true humanistic essence of the Islamic religion, and preservation of our spiritual values on the basis of the principle of "Enlightenment against ignorance" are the basis of reforms in this area. The changing ideological landscape in the international arena, the aggravation of problems in world politics and economics, and the increasing number of supporters of changing the general landscape of the world are manifested as the most important features inherent in the development of the global world. For

example, "in such a situation, we need to fundamentally reconsider the methods of scientific and practical research, analytical and propaganda materials on protecting our society from spiritual threats. It is necessary to form methodological foundations for combating situations of indifference to our universal, national and religious values." Along with many positive processes in our social life, spiritual threats aimed at capturing the hearts and minds of the younger generation are also becoming increasingly dangerous. It is necessary to educate our youth in the spirit of love and devotion to our Motherland, the ideas of independence, and to use their spiritual and educational aspects to realize their talents and abilities, noble aspirations. Perfect mastery of modern science and high technologies has become a decisive factor in the development of any state and society. Great attention is paid to the wide involvement of young people in scientific and innovative activities, to supporting the innovative activities of young scientists. In a rapidly changing world, where various threats and dangers that threaten the stability and security of nations are increasing, it is important to pay special attention to spirituality and enlightenment, to the processes of ideas and ideology. It is precisely modern education and upbringing, high enlightenment that is the main factor of development and prosperity. This is an extremely important issue in improving the education and enlightenment system, adapting young people to modern knowledge, and achieving harmony between education and upbringing in the upbringing of a well-rounded person. To achieve this effectiveness, the head of our country coordinated the activities of the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment in the direction of educational propaganda, relying on the idea of "Enlightenment against ignorance" and organized them on the basis of modern requirements. In today's difficult times, when various threats to establish dialogue between civilizations at the international level are increasing, to form ideological immunity in the minds of young people, to fight against ignorance with enlightenment, to educate the younger generation in the spirit of humanistic ideas, national pride and honor, the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" was adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on the idea of "Enlightenment against ignorance", it is necessary to effectively implement the scientific and historical concept of the spiritual and educational spheres that have been formed in our country for centuries, in order to apply strategic directions, effective, creative and innovative methods of organizing continuous spiritual and educational education and propaganda in society. To do this, first of all,

- Deeply study our rich spiritual and educational heritage and enrich it with the spirit of the present time:
- Formation of a national spiritual system based on the foundations of universal spirituality:

- Creation of mechanisms for the effective use of the media in promoting and agitating for reforms in the spiritual and educational spheres:
- Development of generally recognized ethical principles based on public opinion.

Based on the above principles, the implementation of reforms in the spiritual and educational spheres in our country will certainly not fail to show its results.

Since we have set ourselves the goal of transforming Uzbekistan into a developed country, we can achieve this only through accelerated reforms, science and education, and innovation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate a new generation of cadres who will act as initiative reformers, think strategically, are knowledgeable, and are qualified. Due to current globalization, at a time when the continuous struggle for the human mind and soul is intensifying, various ideological threats and attacks that are being manifested have become a powerful and effective tool for ideological influence on the dynamics of the gradually developing spiritual life of our society. In such a situation, the tasks of creating a strategy for the spiritual development of our society, strengthening the scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations aimed at ensuring its continuity and effectiveness, and further improving the system and mechanism of propaganda and agitation are becoming necessary requirements. The atmosphere of friendship and solidarity prevailing in our country is the most important factor in peace and stability, increasing the effectiveness of the reforms being implemented, and further enhancing the prestige of Uzbekistan in the international arena. Developing a culture of tolerance and humanity. Strengthening interethnic and inter-civil harmony and peace, educating the younger generation on this basis, in the spirit of love for the Motherland and loyalty to the country, has become one of the important priority areas of our state policy. Today, as a result of large-scale reforms and fundamental changes, ensuring freedom of conscience in our country, which is being renewed, has risen to the level of state policy, and major measures are being taken in this regard. Only in this way can we effectively confront all the threats and dangers of today, create a firm immunity against various destructive ideas in our society, and achieve more significant results on the path of democratic development that we have chosen. The words of our enlightened grandfather Mahmudkhoj Behbudi, "Secular science and knowledge are necessary to survive in the world," are still relevant today.

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